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Breath metal oxide sensors

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Introduction

Interest in the research of small-sized gas sensors (especially semiconductor) for medical applications has sharply increased in recent years. Requirements for such sensors are their high sensitivity, performance, and stability to very low concentrations of gases, mainly exhaled by a living organism. One of the most important directions of modern medicine is non-invasive diagnostics of the patient, based on the analysis of exhaled air in a special device. We are talking about the exhaled air, its chemical composition, and volatile substances from the human body through the lungs. It is only necessary to make exhalation and after a few seconds or minutes to get the results of the analysis.

Exhaled breath contains about 1000 volatile organic compounds (VOCs) that are the products of metabolism. The exhaled gases such as NO_x , acetone, ethanol, NH_3 , H_2S , and H_2O_2 can be used as sensors to diagnose various diseases. Several important gases having immediately dangerous to life or health concentration in air. For example, the threshold limit value for ethanol and acetone are 1000 and 750 ppm, correspondingly. Due to the large surface of the lungs, volatile substances (ethanol, ammonia, acetone, and others) very quickly pass from the bloodstream to the external environment with exhaled air. It is the mixture of various molecules secreted by a man that makes up the individual, unique smell of the patient. In a number of cases, this smell allows to immediately make the correct diagnosis. A sharp specific smell from the mouth is a symptom of a number of diseases of the oral cavity and stomach (stomatitis, periodontal disease, gastritis, peptic ulcer, and stomach cancer). In cardiopulmonary insufficiency, unpleasant sour smell of under oxidized metabolic products associated with incomplete combustion of proteins, fats, and carbohydrates in the liver often comes from patients. An unusual persistent smell is a formidable symptom of a growing tumor of the anterior brain. It turned out that with a stroke with an unfavorable outcome, much less acetone is released in patients than in healthy people. At the same time, diabetics, who also fell into a coma, exhale tens and hundreds of times more acetone than healthy ones. The content of acetone and ethanol is significantly different from healthy individuals (in patients with diabetes mellitus, cardiovascular disease, in children with bronchial asthma, diathesis, in pregnant women with toxicities of the first half of pregnancy). We also note that it is possible to successfully detect using semiconductor sensors odorless substances, such as carbon monoxide (carbon monoxide) or carbon dioxide.

1. Detection of diseases

Capabilities of detection of various diseases using the analysis of the breath are discussed below. Data on the surveillance capabilities of diseases in the allocation of specific gases are collected below in Table [1]. Naturally, assembled here material cannot be considered as exhaustive one. Note also that the analysis of the breath allows to detect (diagnose) cancer of stomach and ovaries, rheumatoid disease, acute myocardial infarction, gum disease, tooth decay, bacterial imbalance on the tongue, impacted wisdom teeth, dehydration, sleep apnea, gastric, stomach ulcers duodenal ulcers and other diseases can be carried out.

From the middle of the 20th century to the present day, chromatography and mass spectrograph are among the most widely used analytical methods for studying explosives. In medicine, when studying gas exchange, gas analyzers are used to measure the concentration of carbon dioxide, oxygen, and nitrogen in the inhaled and the exhaled gas mixture, to study blood gases and to measure the concentration of the indicator gas in the artificially created mixture when determining a number of respiration parameters (instruments for measuring gas concentration in a gas mixture). In recent years, ionic and proton mass spectroscopic methods and gas chromatography has been used in medicine, but such equipment is expensive and bulky. Of course, the possibility of physical-chemical studies of gas-phase are not limited to the analysis. Samples of internal abdominal gases can collect and examine from different sections of the bronchi with bronchoscopy, from the stomach with gastroscopy, from the colon with colonoscopy, from the bladder with cystoscopy, from the uterus during hysteroscopy. Today we are talking about the possibility of developing individual metabolic profile of the patient.

The use of semiconductor gas sensors for detecting the concentration of detectable gas released in patients (acetone in diabetes, for example) is widely discussed in the literature [32, 38]. Determination of the concentration of chemical compounds in explosives using gas sensors will allow the diagnosis of the disease already in the early stages and will make it possible to control treatment. In addition to nitrogen, oxygen, and water vapor, explosives contain various gases in a sick person. By the concentration of acetone and the amount of current or voltage passing through the semiconductor sensor, for example, one can judge the degree of diabetes, acute heart failure, lung cancer; hydrogen peroxide and nitric oxide-asthma and other pulmonary diseases, cancer of the digestive system; ammonia and hydrogen sulfide - hepatitis and cirrhosis; hydrogen and methane, a number of diseases of the digestive system, etc. The current study of head, ovarian, bladder, prostate, kidney, gastric, and neck cancer, Crohn's disease, ulcerative colitis. idio-

pathic and atypical Parkinson's, multiple sclerosis, pulmonary hypertension and other diseases is started now using nanoarrays and artificial intelligence methods.

Table

Gases	Exhalation and diagnostic significance
Nitrogen oxide(NO)	Respiratory diseases [asthma, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), etc.] Rhinitis digestive diseases [inflammation in the stomach (gastritis, hepatitis, colitis), including infection Helicobacter pylori digestive cancer] Hyperthermia Heavy-textured sepsis Uremia
Carbon monoxide (CO)	Anemia (hemolytic, sideroblastic cell) Carboxy hemoglobinemia in acute and chronic exposures Lasting stay at intakes Giperbilirubinemia of newborn oxidative stress hematoma Hemoglobinuria Pre-eclampsia of infection Thalassemia respiratory diseases (asthma, COPD, infections of the respiratory infection Inflammation of lung)
Ammonia (NH ₃)	Diseases of the kidneys and liver (renal insufficiency in nephritis, idiopathic hypertension, atherosclerosis of renal artery, toxicosis and nephropathy of pregnant, toxic defeats of kidneys, paucity of the liver in jaundice, hepatitis, cirrhosis of the liver, toxic hepatitis) Acute and chronic radiation sickness The metabolism of monoamine in light Uremia
Hydrogen (H ₂)	Diseases of bodies of digestion (digestive disorders of infants Gastrointestinal Disorders anaerobic bacteria in the large intestine Malabsorption hydrocarbons)
Hydrogen Peroxide H ₂ O ₂	Respiratory diseases (asthma, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), lung cancer Weakened respiratory lung function, etc.) The acute and chronic radiation sickness Diabetes
Methane	Gastrointestinal disorders (Malabsorption hydrocarbons) Colorectal cancer
CS ₂ and pentane	Risk factor in coronary artery diseases, Schizophrenia
Ethylene (C ₂ H ₄)	Oxygen stress, Lipid peroxidation internal at acute myocardial infarction Destruction caused by free radicals Uremia
Ethane (C ₂ H ₆) and pentane	Lipid peroxidation in liver transplant peroxide Marker-assisted oxidation of lipids Schizophrenia COPD Interstitial lung disease Asthma Cystic fibrosis Heart failure Inflammatory bowel disease
Methanol	Diseases of the central nervous system Lung and breast cancer
Ethanol	Alcoholism Diabetes
Acetone C ₆ H ₆ O	Alcoholism, the function of the pancreas in acute pancreatitis and execute-destructive dietary and severe balance failure at lung cancer Diabetes Chronic liver disease
Isotopic modification	Infection with the bacterium Helicobacter pylori passage of food through the gastrointestinal tract the overgrowth of bacteria lactose Digestion pancreatic Dysfunction Malabsorption liver dysfunction, including cirrhosis the metabolism of bile glucose metabolism
Vapors of urine	Gastroenterology
Pentane and its Derivatives	Breath and lung cancer. Acute myocardial infarction Heart titrant rejection Rheumatic arthritis The exacerbation of asthma
Alkanes (hexane, etc.)	Lung cancer Tuberculosis
Dimethyl and carbonyl sulfides	Lung cancer Cystic fibrosis Intra- and extraoral halitosis Chronic liver disease Hypermethioninemia
Isoprene	Lung cancer Castaic ulcer Heart failure
Hydrogen sulfide	Intraoral halitosis
Heptane, xylenes, octane, ethylbenzene, styrene, decane, toluene, benzene, gaseous aldehyde and formaldehyde	Lung cancer

Metal oxide semiconductors n-type SnO₂, ZnO, WO₃, TiO₂, MoO₃, In₂O₃, Fe₂O₃ and p-type CuO, NiO, Cr₂O₃, Mn₃O₄ are used during breath analysis [1,2,32,33]. Some interesting papers about breath analysis listed in Refs. [13, 15, 22, 31, 34, 35]. Note that the disease diagnosis using exhaled breath is still in the nascent stage and needs further improvement for clinical applications.

2. Detection of NO₂ and NH₃ for the diagnosis of asthma and renal disease

Villi-like WO₃ nanostructures show high gas responses ($R_{\text{gas}}/R_{\text{air}} \sim 30$ to 0.2 ppm NO at 200 °C [21]. It is shown also that WO₃ nanotubes exhibit high responses to 1 ppm NO. These results were obtained in highly humid (RH > 80%) atmospheres. BOSCH Healthcare Solutions announced a monitor which allowing measurements of fractional exhaled nitric oxide (FENO) for the diagnosis of asthma [16, 17]. Therefore, the potential of WO₃ nanostructures for the diagnosis of asthma was demonstrated. This device consists of

pretreatment components that precondition the exhaled gas and sensing components that measure FENO.

The initial stages of renal disease can be diagnosed by measuring NH_3 vapor in exhaled breath [26]. End-stage renal disease (ESRD) requires time-consuming, expensive, and inconvenient hemodialysis, which significantly decreases the quality of life for patients. If the nephron function is completely lost, kidney transplantation needs to be considered. The breath NH_3 concentration of ESRD patients ranges around 4.9 ppm in contrast to 0.96 ppm for healthy individuals [26]. Exhaled ammonia can be also used to diagnose liver disease and helicobacter pylori infection. $\alpha\text{-MoO}_3$ has high selectivity to NH_3 detection at sub-ppm levels even in highly humid atmospheres [27]. It can be used for diagnosis of renal failure. MoO_3 and WO_3 often show high response to basic amines such as trimethylamine, triethylamine, and butylamine.

3. Detection of acetone for diagnosing diabetes

Diabetes patients use fat instead of glucose for energy and ketones are produced by the liver during fatty-acid metabolism. The concentrations of breath acetone in diabetes patients are reported to be higher than 1.8 ppm while those of healthy people are lower than 0.8 ppm [37]. Breath acetone concentrations can increase during ketogenic or low carbohydrate diets that are known to induce ketosis. It allows checking the effectiveness of ketosis-based dietary programs for healthy people. Among all other sensing materials, metal oxides show the highest responses to acetone. Various oxide sensing materials mentioned below allow to enhance selectivity and sensitivity to acetone under highly humid atmospheres.

There are Pt, Rh or Ni-loaded WO_3 hemitubes/nanofibers, having an average size of 2 to 3 nm, Si-doped $\epsilon\text{-WO}_3$ [24], Pt-loaded SnO_2 nanotubes/hierarchical nanofibers [22], Pd-loaded $\text{ZnO}/\text{ZnCo}_2\text{O}_4$ hollow spheres [24], RuO_2 -loaded WO_3 nanofibers [28], Rh_2O_3 -loaded WO_3 nanofibers [23], and PdO-loaded Co_3O_4 hollow nanocages [24]. These fabricated nanostructures show great promise to be utilized as portable breath sensors for diabetes disease diagnosis.

Note that SnO_2 , ZnO , Fe_2O_3 , and other metal oxide gas sensors often show similar responses to acetone and ethanol [7]. Accordingly, analyses from intoxicated diabetes patients, or the presence of small amounts of alcohol in the mouth, may not provide reliable diagnoses. Pure and catalyst loaded WO_3 have been used as the most common and representative sensing materials for the selective detection of acetone [20, 24].

4. Detection of H_2S for diagnosing halitosis

The degradation of S-containing amino acids in the oral cavity, upper/lower respiratory tract, and alveolar exchange with blood lead to halitosis. It is detectable as highly odorous gases with concentrations less than 1 ppm, that can be used to diagnose fetor hepaticus and metabolic disorder.

CuO alone and as additive materials to SnO_2 , In_2O_3 , and ZnO has been used as sensing material. The conversion of the p-type semiconducting CuO into metallic CuS leads to form of junction n-type semiconductor-metallic CuS . The doping of hollow SnO_2

spheres with CuO decreased the humidity dependence of the sensing characteristics to negligible levels without sacrificing high selectivity and sensitivity H_2S at 80% RH. Therefore, CuO is effective both in dry air and exhaled breath.

Liang et al. [28] reported that the CuO -loaded In_2O_3 nanofiber sensor showed reversible H_2S sensing characteristics above 300 °C. Doping Mo on ZnO nanowires not only increased selectivity to H_2S but also significantly enhanced the reversibility of the H_2S sensing characteristics. Ag was also reported to be an effective additive that enhanced the H_2S selectivity of sensors based on TiO_2 [30]. Yoneda et al. [39] provided a mini review on various techniques for the analysis of halitosis.

5. Detection of volatile organic compounds for lung cancer diagnosis

Researchers have investigated different gases of lung cancer by comparing the breaths of healthy people and lung cancer patients [19]. Volatile organic compounds (VOCs) are reported as biomarker gases of lung cancer. Comprehensive review on VOCs related to lung cancer has been provided by Hakim et al. [18]. Note that most lung-cancer biomarker gases, except a few, contain benzene rings. Pure CNT or graphene-based sensing materials generally do not exhibit notable responses to large gases at room temperature or temperatures less than 100°C.

P-type semiconductors as gas sensing materials for benzene-derived gases, such as xylene, toluene, and benzene itself, can be used during measurements of lung cancer.

Gaseous aldehyde and formaldehyde breath biomarkers of lung cancer were proposed [22]. Ni-doped and Co-doped ZnO nanowires, Co_3O_4 (mesoporous, Cr-doped nanocomposites, and Pd-loaded shell sphere and hierarchical nanosheets), $\text{Cr}/\text{r}2\text{O}_3\text{-ZnCr}_2\text{O}_4$ nanocomposites, NiO-NiMoO₄-SnO₂ nanocomposites, Cr-doped NiO hierarchical nanosheets, Pd-SnO₂ film with Co_3O_4 overlayer are very promising materials for detection of lung cancer. [1, 2, 38].

Of course, lung cancer can be diagnosed via the detection of a single biomarker gas. However, to increase diagnosis precision, the diagnosis of lung cancer using the electronic nose technology is preferable. Note also that pretreatment components such as dehumidifiers, preconcentrators, and flow sensors are very important for precise analysis. To miniaturize the system and achieve *in situ* diagnosis, the adsorption of analytic gases, interference gases, and moisture needs to be significantly improved [38].

6. YSU detectors of gases

An intensive work has been started on a manufacture of corresponding new small-sized equipment using semiconductor gas sensors. Note that at Yerevan State University (Department of Semiconductor Physics and Microelectronics and the Scientific Center for Semiconductor Devices and Nanoelectronics) as a result of many years of research, semiconductor sensors of various gases have been developed. Sensors at YSU are sensitive to vapors of acetone, ammonia, nitrogen oxides, iso-butane, ammonia, hydrogen sulfide, hydrogen, various alcohols, toluene, combustible gases, hydrogen peroxide, propane, propylene glycol, formalde-

hyde, dimethylformamide, dichloroethane, gasoline, carbon monoxide and smoke arising in the early stages of a fire (see some references [6, 8-12]). As part of a NATO grant, small-sized semiconductor sensors for nerve gases of chemical weapons (sarin, mustard gas) have been developed in YSU. Successful tests of such

sensors were carried out at the Czech Military Academy. Of course, there is information about commercial gas sensors (except for military, poisonous and a number of industrial gases) produced in the USA, Japan, China, Russia and Germany. Note that

Fig. 1 Hydrogen leakage sensor [3]

Fig. 2. Ethanol sensor [10]

Fig. 3. Arduino Nano Sensor [11].

the sensors at YSU are stable in time, of smaller volume, much cheaper than produced in above-mentioned countries and are easily compatible with integrated circuits. Figures 1 – 3 show our small-sized detectors of hydrogen and alcohols [3, 11, 12]. Fig. 3 show the possibility of implementing such a detector using a programmable board and the Arduino Nano memory. It is possible to load a program into the Arduino processor that will control all of these devices according to a given algorithm. It is noteworthy that as a gas sensor can be used as sensors proposed in the center of semiconductor devices and nanotechnology of YSU, as well as any others. Earlier, we developed also a device, which allows us to measure simultaneously three gases — methane, carbon monoxide, and hydrogen [12].

Conclusions

One of the most important directions of modern medicine is non-invasive diagnostics of the patient,

based on the analysis of exhaled air in a special device. Data on the surveillance capabilities of various diseases in the allocation of specific gases are collected. The potential of various semiconductor chemical resistors made from metal oxide semiconductors to diagnose disease has been reviewed. For disease diagnosis from exhaled breath, pure and catalyst-loaded semiconductor chemical resistors sensing materials for specific biomarker gases are reported. In particular, nanosensors were discussed having the potential to detect asthma, renal disease, diabetes, halitosis, and lung cancer. The humidity and temperature dependencies of various sensing characteristics need to be decreased to negligible levels through the complete understanding of gas-sensing mechanisms and the interaction between moisture and the sensing surface. Corresponding low-cost detectors are developed which can detect small concentrations of exhaled air.

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